

SOME PSYCHOLOGICAL PROBLEMS IN THE FORMATION OF A CHILD AS A PERSON

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Annotation: The personality of the child develops not only in the interaction of biological factors, but also in the interaction of individual and social psychological characteristics. It should be noted that in the field of psychology there are also theorists who put biological development above psychological development factors.

Key words: child, psychological factor, psychology, psyche, development, biological development, practice, experience, activity, consciousness

Looking at this issue as a psychological factor, the scientific views of psychologists studying the development of children's psyche and leading practitioners are noteworthy. In Particular, S.L.Rubinstein, L.S.Vigotsky, Z.Freud, D.S.Hall, P.P.Blonsky, D.X.Jackson, F.Holsman, A.N.Leontev, A.R.Luria, E.Krechmer, J.Piaje, S.Scribner, K.Goldstein, G.S.Sullivan, Ya.Kazanin, X.Werner, B.Kaplan and many other psychologist scientists have expressed valuable scientific and practical opinions and opinions on this problem. Of These, L.S.Vigotsky believes that one of the manifestations of psychological lag in Child Development is the inability to master word concepts in relation to the age of the child or an imbalance in relation to his age in actions¹. The child cannot fully and qualitatively cope with the task of controlling his spiritual inner self, that is, reflectivity in relation to the object of external influence. As a result of this, the child lags behind development, and external and internal movement cannot ensure the formation of mental characteristics, as a result of which Sharp imbalances in the child's actions towards their peers begin to be felt. It can be seen that the personality of the child develops not only in the interaction of biological factors, but also in the interaction of individual and sociopsychological characteristics. It should be noted that in the field of psychology there are also theorists who put biological development above psychological development factors. Including biogenetic theorists and Z.Freud and his disciples recognized that instincts governing human activity are the main factor passed down from generation to generation – a trait, an innate product, a force that drives initial unconscious needs and inclinations².

The English genetic scientist Sh.Aurbach implies that the level of mental development of the child, special abilities in the child, individual qualities of the child are innate, and these pre-existing factors determine the characteristics of the environment³. Australian psychologist K.While Bauler considered the genetic factor leading not only in the mental development of the child, but also in the development of moral quality, the American psychologist and

¹ Выготский Л.С. Собрание сочинений. 3-т. – М.: «Педагогика», 1984. –С. 30.

² Леонтьев А.Н. Возникновение и эволюция психики. Избранные психологические произведения. В 2 т. – М.: «Педагогика», 1983. –С. 142-166.

³ Валлон А. Психическое развитие ребенка. – М.: «Просвещение», 1967. –С. 28.

educator D.Dewey applies the idea that " human nature cannot be changed, heredity determines human nature". The opinions of the aforementioned psychologists and educators on the personality of the child and its formation, of course, consist of a one-sided approach, which did not take into account such factors as the psychophysiological state of the fetus and the factors affecting it during the perenatal period,the social environment, interpersonal relationships, education. In fact, in the field of psychology, there are concepts of Man, person and individuality that give harmony to each other, but, qualitatively, one is fundamentally different from the other. When we look at a person biologically, he belongs to the class of mammals, a biological creature, an upright gait at the expense of ontogenetic development, the adaptation of his hands to labor activity, the possession of a highly progressive brain, etc., indicates his uniqueness.

In terms of socialization, however, it is implied that a person is armed with consciousness, through which he can also perceive being. As a person, a person is an active conscious member of society, the owner of consciousness who, with the help of his speech, is able to share his impressions with others on the basis of certain norms, and be able to influence others with his own consciousness. And the individuality of a person is determined by the uniqueness of all people in the world, the uniqueness of the nature of each of them, the intellectual, emotional, volitional qualities of which they are. Among these, it can be seen that a person, in addition to his innate set of vision, hearing, perception, feeling, appetite and other characteristics, goes to saturate life circumstances and activities with moral and normative qualities based on educational influence. The famous Russian psychologist S.L.In Rubinstein's interpretation, "... an individual is a complex of internal conditions that change the direction of external influences". Another of the issues that are problematic in the field of psychology and have different views is the question of which genetic, innate, acquired or social factors are leading in the development of the human psyche. For example, the anatomical-physiological characteristics of the child, which he appropriated as inheritance from his own parents, represent the structure of the arms, legs, face, etc. Psychologically, its adaptation to the environment, free movement, figurative reflection of things and phenomena in its consciousness is considered a general process, and to what extent its implementation differs in each person. Because, when a person enters into a relationship with the external world, the acquired or inherited quality in it has a negative effect on the human psyche, on the condition of the passed-through anatomical anomaly (regress) (hip of the limbs, too low height, imbalance of body structure, etc.), on its finding its place in society. That is why it cannot be denied that the external environment has an influence on the development of the child's psyche as a leading factor. Leading psychologist scientists L.S.Vigotsky, S.Rubinstein, A.Leontev and others have recognized the influence of the social environment as a leading factor on the formation of a child as a perfect person, without denying the role of generational heritage⁴. Psychologist scientists V.N.Kolbonovsky, A.R.Luria and A.N. Mironov studies show that even in Twins from one egg cell, in the same natural conditions, combinatorics according to educational methods, that is, completely different in certain types of creative activity-other results were obtained. So, in the formation of a child as a perfect person, we will have made mistakes in both concepts, if we say that the factors passed from generation to generation are leading, external factors are simply a tool or a social environment is leading, and the factors

⁴ Леонтьев А.Н. Развитие высших форм запоминания. – М.: 1983. –С. 83-88.

passed from parent to gene are not fundamental. If, on the basis of their equal and appropriate cooperation, we can provide the child with the right education, then only then can we form the child as a perfect person.

A number of social and biological factors, such as properly organized education for the child, the nature of the interaction of the family and members in it, the social groups in which the child communicates, the profession he chooses, the perfection of the child's internal mental capabilities, the formation of personality, self-awareness and attitude towards others, and its Many Eastern allomas have also expressed their opinions on this order. In particular, Abu Nasr Farabi, in his work "the city of sensitive people", makes an excellent observation about man and his psyche, recognizing that the development of the human psyche is directly dependent on biological and environmental factors, and is formed under the influence of these factors. Ibn Sina, in his work "the laws of Tib", cited valuable information about the structure of the human body, the physiological processes in it and the mental factors that are in direct contact with them, their impact on the human body. The main issue in Yusuf Khos Hajib's "Qutadgü bilig" is the upbringing of a perfect person, Abdurahman Jami's "Baharistan", "Tuhfatul Ahror" and other works reflect on teaching a child to a learned, enlightened, educated and professional, while Alisher Navoi in his "Khazoyinul-maoniy", "Mahbub-ul qulub" and other works expressed wonderful thoughts about a mature, harmonious person, his morality and ability. In addition, Babur, Furqat, Bedil, Fergani, Mashrab, Gulkhani, Nodira, Uvaysi, Muqimi, Hazi, Avlani and many other thinkers, writers, poets and poets also paid special attention to the issues of youth education, character, family life issues and interpersonal relations in their works. So, scientifically based thoughts and life experiences show that if a child is biologically healthy from the parent, four mules do not come into the world of idols (the child is observed a state of anomaly (regression)), it remains as a difficult matter to find a solution to form him as a mentally proportional and perfect person.

In conclusion, paying special attention to the factors that indicate its positive or negative impact on the development of the child puts on the responsibility of educators and teachers, as well as fathers. Among the conditions and factors that they should pay attention to, we can cite the following as examples: hereditary factors of a child passed from generation to generation, a healthy or unhealthy environment in the family, an organized hygienic or non-hygienic environment for a child, a healthy and properly organized or unhealthy educational environment inappropriate for the young age of a child, environmental

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